

Integrating Structural Biology

Instruct-ULTRA

WP7 – Streamlining Access Procedures for Pioneering Structural Biology Methods

Lead Beneficiaries: P10 - CNRS

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Deliverable D7.1: Standardised workflows for production, crystallisation and data collection of membrane proteins

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Project objective

To streamline procedures for the structural analysis of membrane proteins.

Executive summary

Workflows have been developed for the expression of integral membrane proteins (IMPs) in three different contexts: mammalian IMPs in human embryonic kidney cells (expi293F™); mammalian IMPs in *Trichoplusia ni* cells (High Five™) insect cells; and bacterial IMPs expressed in *E. coli*. Two common features of the workflows were cost-effective testing for expression in small culture volumes (1- 15 ml) and fusion to a fluorescent reporter protein (GFP or mCherry) to analyse expression and/or detergent solubilisation. The protocols developed for the expression of membrane proteins in human and insect cells were compared by analysing the same six targets, selected from different subcellular locations (plasma membrane, endoplasmic reticulum (ER) membrane, and Golgi apparatus membrane). The six targets were transiently transfected at small-scale into either expi293F™ or Hi5 High Five™ cells and analysis of fluorescence showed that all were expressed, though differences in the levels of protein produced were observed between the two expression cell systems. Work is on-going to purify proteins from both expression systems for subsequent structural studies by cryo-EM. The protocol for the production of bacterial membrane proteins in *E. coli* was

exemplified by the analysis of two enzyme families from mycobacteria involved in cell wall synthesis (Arabinosyltransferase and Arabinofuranosyltransferase). The results demonstrated the critical importance of selecting homologues from multiple species and screening these for expression in parallel at small scale. Approximately 50 % of the cloned genes were expressed and from these, eight proteins were purified and structural studies initiated by cryo-electron microscopy.

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1. General Introduction

Membrane proteins account for up to a third of proteins encoded in genomes¹ of both eukaryotes and prokaryotes. They perform a wide array of vital functions in the cell and are the major therapeutic targets of approved drugs². Rapid advances in cryo-EM technology are set to accelerate the determination of membrane protein structures but their production remains laborious involving overexpression in heterologous systems, detergent-mediated extraction from the cell and purification. Thus, preparation of samples is the rate-limiting step in structural studies of membrane proteins. Therefore, the focus of the work described in this report has been on the initial stages of sample preparation and use of the appropriate expression system for protein production. The majority of integral membrane protein (IMP) structures deposited in the ProteinDataBank (PDB) are from prokaryotes and therefore *E. coli* is the dominant expression host for their production. By contrast the majority of mammalian IMPs have been expressed in eukaryotic cells. This reflects the need for specific chaperones and/or post-translation modifications (e.g. glycosylation and palmitoylation) that are not found in *E. coli*. In this report we describe the development of streamlined processes for the production of both eukaryotic and prokaryotic membrane proteins expressed in mammalian or insect cells and *E. coli* respectively.

2. Expression of membrane proteins in mammalian cells (P2)

2.1 Introduction

Analysis of the expression systems used for the production of human IMP based on structures deposited in the PDB shows that Human Embryonic Kidney (HEK) cells, are the second most used system, after baculovirus/insect cells (Figure 1).

¹Almén SM, Nordström KJV, Fredriksson R and HB Schiöth (2009) Mapping the human membrane proteome: A majority of the human membrane proteins can be classified according to function and evolutionary origin. *BMC Biology*. 7(50):1-14.

²Santos R, Ursu O, Gaulton A et al., (2017) A comprehensive map of molecular drug targets. *Nat Rev Drug Discov*. 16(1):19–34.

³Goehring A, Lee CH, Wang KH et al. (2014) Screening and large-scale expression of membrane proteins in mammalian cells for structural studies. *Nat Protocol*. 9(11):2574-85

Figure 1. Expression hosts used to produce human membrane proteins for downstream structural analysis. The majority of targets with the determined structure were produced in insect and HEK293 expression systems.

Therefore, the use of HEK cells for IMP production was streamlined, focusing on screening for expression, extraction and purification at small scale to produce a cost-effective workflow. To develop and test the protocol, six IMPs were selected, each with a different subcellular localisation (plasma membrane, endoplasmic reticulum (ER) membrane, and Golgi apparatus membrane) (Table 1).

Gene Name	Protein name	Localisation	Source	No. TM helices	Mol. weight kDa
<i>Ntsr1</i>	Neurotensin receptor 1	PM	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	7	47
<i>SLC10A1</i>	Sodium/bile acid cotransporter	PM	<i>Bos taurus</i>	9	41
<i>ADORA2A</i>	Adenosine receptor A2a	PM	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	7	45
<i>SLC6A1</i>	GABA transporter 1	PM	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	12	67
<i>SLC35D1</i>	UDP-glucuronic acid/UDP-N-acetylgalactosamine transporter	ER	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	8	39
<i>SLC35D2</i>	UDP-N-acetylglucosamine/UDP-glucose/GDP-mannose transporter	Golgi	<i>Homo sapiens</i>	10	37

Table 1. Summary of selected mammalian integral membrane proteins

2.2 Expi293F mammalian cells - Optimising expression

The six target genes were inserted into the vectors pOPINE-3C-GFP-his₈ and/or pOPIN-3C-Strep2-His₈ by Infusion cloning³. The carboxy-terminal fusion to either eGFP or mVENUS enabled expression of the genes to be tracked and quantified. Suspension cultured HEK Expi293F cells were transiently transfected at 1.0 ml culture volumes using polyethylenimine and a protocol that has been optimised in-house. The effect of temperature (30 vs 37°C) and time to harvest (1 to 6 days) were investigated by following eGFP fluorescence and cell viability. The results showed that products were subjected to proteolytic breakdown during

³Berrow, N, Alderton, D., Sainsbury 3, et al. (2007) A Versatile Ligation-Independent Cloning Method Suitable for High-Throughput Expression Screening Applications *Nucleic Acids Res* 35 (6), e45 2007

growth of cells at 37 °C for either 3 or 6 days, depending on the target (Table 2). The growth conditions for maximising production of intact proteins were shown to be 30 °C for 6 days and all further expression studies were carried out under these conditions.

	<i>Ntsr1</i>	<i>SLC10A1</i>	<i>ADORA2A</i>	<i>SLC6A1</i>	<i>SLC35D1</i>	<i>SLC35D2</i>
30°C, 3 Days	+	+	+	+	+	+
30°C, 6 Days	+	+	+	+	+	+
37°C, 3 Days	Proteolysis	Proteolysis	+	+	Proteolysis	+
37°C, 6 Days	Proteolysis	Proteolysis	Proteolysis	Proteolysis	Proteolysis	Proteolysis

Table 2. Results of the expression of the six membrane protein targets in Expi293F cells grown at a temperature of either 30°C or 37°C.

The expression of the six target IMPs were compared in terms of the time course and the level and quality of the final products, by monitoring GFP fluorescence in whole cells and lysates (Figures 2 and 3). Although transfection efficiency for all targets was approximately the same (25 – 30 %), the yields varied: *SLC10A1* = *ADORA2A* > *SLC6A1* = *SLC35D1* = *SLC35D2*. However, all proteins were shown to be intact by SDS-PAGE, confirming that the fluorescence signals corresponded to full-length products.

Figure 2. Visualisation of GFP-fused protein expression. In-cell GFP fluorescence signals images of targets expressed in Expi293F cells at 30°C at different time points captured with EVOS fluorescent microscope. Already at 24 hours post-transfection, the GFP signals for target proteins are detected. With enhancers and after longer expression (2-6 Days in total) the progress in GFP fluorescence is observed.

Figure 3. Analysis of GFP-fused protein expressions. Left panel: Quantification of GFP fluorescence in living cells using Tali imaging-based cytometer system (Thermofisher Scientific) **(A)** Progression of the number of cells expressing GFP-fused targets and **(B)** GFP yield over days is shown. Highest GFP signals are observed at the end of expression (Day 6 after transfection). Right panel: GFP fluorescence of target proteins after 6 Days expression in **(C)** cell pellets and **(D)** in treated probes before and after SDS-PAGE run.

2.3 Optimising membrane protein extraction/solubilisation

Having optimised the transient expression protocol, the next step was to find an appropriate detergent for the extraction of proteins from cell membranes for subsequent affinity (Ni-NTA) purification. Therefore, a set of single detergents or mixed micelles were assembled for evaluation (Table 3).

N	Detergent	cmc, %	Final concentration, %	Stock solution, %	Detergent type
1	CYMAL-5	0.12	1.2	12	Nonionic
2	CYMAL-6	0.028	0.3	2.8	Nonionic
3	LDAO	0.023	0.2	2.3	Zwitterionic
4	Fos-12	0.047	0.5	5	Zwitterionic
5	DM	0.087	1	8.7	Nonionic
6	OG	0.53	1	10	Nonionic
7	Triton X-100	0.01	0.1	1	Nonionic
8	DDM	0.01	1	1	Nonionic
9	DDM + DM	n/d	1 + 1	n/d	Mixed
10	DDM + LDAO	n/d	1 + 0.2	n/d	Mixed
11	DDM + Triton X-100	n/d	1 + 0.1	n/d	Mixed

Table 3. List of detergents

Transient expression of IMPs was scaled up to 100 ml culture volumes and total membrane fractions prepared from the cells were harvested after 6 days at 30 °C. Cells were broken by sonication and centrifuged at 3000 g for 35 min at 4°C to remove unbroken cell debris. The membrane fractions were collected from the cleared lysates by ultracentrifugation at 230,000 g for 2 hours at 4°C. Solubilised samples were analysed by in-gel fluorescence and incubated with Ni-NTA beads to pull-down the His-tagged IMPs, which were analysed on Coomassie stained gels. CYMAL-6 was the only detergent that extracted all targets with good efficiency, though solubilised yield was greater with other detergents for some of the targets. Mixed micelles provided very good solubilisation for most of the non GPCR Targets (Figure 4). Most of the detergent solubilised proteins could be bound to and eluted from Ni-NTA beads and hence partially purified (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Detergents screening for solubilisation and purification of membrane proteins. **(A)** In-Gel GFP fluorescence signals of Targets solubilised in different detergents. **(B)** In-Gel GFP fluorescence signals and **(C)** Coomassie-stained protein bands of targets purified in different detergents via Ni-NTA. **(D)** Plotted GFP intensities of Targets extracted in different detergents. **(E)** Plotted GFP intensities of proteins purified in different detergents.

2.4 Pilot Purification of H.s. SLC6A1

Using the optimised workflow, human GABA transporter fused to GFP (*H.s. SLC6A1*) has been purified as a stable dimer from 100 ml cell culture volume (Figure 5). The quality of the partially purified IMPs was assessed by fluorescence-coupled size exclusion chromatography (FSEC) and it was shown that not only the choice of detergent but also buffer composition is essential to prevent the dissociation of protein oligomers (Figure 6). Further studies will address the stability of purified samples, protein quality on EM grids (negative stain) and if required, protein reconstitution in one of the alternative detergent-free systems (e.g. peptidisks, amphipols or other equivalents).

Figure 5. FSEC analysis of protein stability in different detergents. **(A)** Representative In-Gel GFP fluorescence and Coomassie staining of *SLC6A1* target extracted and purified in different detergents. **(B)** FSEC analysis of *SLC6A1* target purified in different detergents via Ni-NTA. **(C)** Comparison of protein fluorescence yields in different detergents.

Figure 6. Screen of additives for improving the stability of *SLC6A1* dimer. The FSEC traces of *SLC6A1* target purified with and without the addition of $MgSO_4$ indicate the essential role of divalent cations for oligomer (in this case, dimer) stability

The workflow for small-scale expression tests and quality control of samples is summarised in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Summary of the workflow for the optimising the production of membrane proteins by transient expression in expi293F cells.

3. High Five (Hi5) insect cells (P1 third party)

3.1 Introduction

Insect cell expression systems have been used extensively in production of human integral membrane proteins (IMPs) because of their advantages for carrying out post-translation modification, processing and sorting of proteins similar to mammalian expression systems. Although Baculoviral expression system in insect cells is widely used, it has some disadvantages, such as the longer time required to produce the protein (2-4 weeks). Additionally, the lysis of the cells and the release of baculoviral particles hampers protein purification. This increases the resources required for screening and production of the protein. To overcome this, a high throughput method has been established for analysis of expressible constructs for membrane proteins in Hi5 insect cells using transient gene expression (TGE). To allow for comparison with the results from transient expi293 cells (section 2), the same six targets have been expressed.

3.2 Vector construction

Genes encoding the same set of six target membrane proteins (Table 1) were cloned into the pOpiE2 expression vector in frame with mCherry as a C-terminal fluorescent tag including the Twin-Strep purification tag (Figure 8). These recombinant plasmids were used for transient gene expression (TGE) in insect (Hi5) cells, using protocols which were optimised in-house to follow the expression of membrane proteins on a small scale.

Figure 8. Microscopic fluorescence analysis of pOpiE2-C6 expression constructs in insect cells and schematic representation of the cloning strategy to screen membrane protein expression. **(A)** The expression of membrane proteins in High Five cells at 48hrs post transfection by TGE was detected by using EVOS fluorescence microscope. Red fluorescence (E_{x585nm} , E_{m624nm}) was localised at either the cell wall or intracellular ER structures. T1(Ntsr1); T2(SLC10A1); T3(ADORA2A); T4SLC6A1); T5(SLC35D1); T6 (SLC36D2).It was shown that all the target membrane proteins could be expressed successfully. **(B)** Schematic diagram of expression vectors with C-terminally fused fluorescence (mCherry) and purification (Twin-Strep) tags. C6 & C7 are the respective in-house numbers for the pOpiE2 vectors, correlating to the orientation of the C-terminal tags.

3.3 Measuring expression

The expression of the IMPs was monitored by measuring the mCherry fluorescence of the cells by flow cytometry in High Five cells daily. The mCherry expression in cells plateaued after 72hrs and no further increase in fluorescence was observed, although the viability remained greater than 93%. The transfection efficiency of all targets was in the range of 35 - 40%, with an exception of T6 (SLC35-D2) which only reached 20% (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Expression profile and analysis of mCherry fused IMPs in pOpIE2-C6. Quantification of mCherry fluorescence was performed using an Accuri C6 flow cytometer. **(A)** Transfection efficiencies for all six IMPs targets **(B)** Total mCherry yield as mean fluorescence intensity for the daily samples. The maximum expression was observed at 48hrs post transfection, later attained a plateau. **(C)** Western blot of soluble cell fraction (diluted 1:10) using anti-mCherry antibody (Abcam). The expected size of the protein in kDa is shown in brackets.

From western blot analysis (Figure 9C) varying levels of expression of the fusion protein to mCherry could be detected. However, direct expression of mCherry could be detected for T3 (ADORA2A). This might be due to the availability of an in-frame downstream ATG site in the Twin-Strep-tag region or partial proteolysis in the cells. The alternative C7 vector series (Figure 8B), with the Twin-Strep-tag fused to the C-term of mCherry, will also be evaluated for production of full-length fusion protein by western blot analysis, using anti-mCherry and anti-Strep antibodies. Full-length protein will be purified by affinity chromatography. The workflow is summarised in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Summary of the workflow for production of membrane proteins by transient expression in insect cells.

3.4 Streamlining production

The pipeline for initial, small-scale membrane protein expression using mCherry fluorescence has been successfully established for all constructs. β -test users could subsequently be invited to apply for screening for expressible constructs for membrane proteins in High Five insect cells. The first candidate was selected and invited to send the construct for the initial screening, to enable the project work to continue beyond the scope of this deliverable.

4. Expression of membrane proteins in *E. coli* cells (P14)

4.1 Introduction

An efficient workflow has been developed for screening, scaling and purifying membrane proteins expressed in *E. coli*. To exemplify the protocol, two families of IMPs from *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* were selected for analysis. The unique cell envelope structure of *M. tuberculosis* which is composed mainly of mycolic acids, arabinogalactan, peptidoglycan and lipoarabinomannan, accounts for its unusual low permeability and resistance towards common antibiotics⁴. To date, no 3D structure of any target protein from Arabinosyltransferase (EmbA-C) or Arabinofuranosyltransferase (AftA-D) families is known, and studies about them are still very scarce at the protein level, likely due to low levels of expression and difficulties in purifying these membrane proteins. The anti-tuberculosis agent ethambutol targets arabinogalactan biosynthesis through inhibition of Emb, but not Aft enzymes⁵. The emergence

⁴Jankute, M., et al. "Assembly of the Mycobacterial Cell Wall." *Annu Rev Microbiol* 69: 405-423. (2015)

⁵Jankute, S. Grover, A. K. Rana, G. S. Besra, Arabinogalactan and lipoarabinomannan biosynthesis: structure, biogenesis and their potential as drug targets. *Future Microbiology* 7, 129-147 (2012).

of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis is a serious threat to global TB control and has prompted the need to characterise the structures of these target proteins to unravel the binding site of the substrates and current drugs. This will give insights into the mechanism of drug-resistance (Embs+ ethambutol) and may provide templates (Afts) for the rational design of a much-needed new generation of therapeutics against tuberculosis.

4.2 Methods

A total of 97 AftA-D and EmbA-C genes were identified from 15 Mycobacteria species. Primers were designed for cloning into plasmid pNYCOMPS⁶ (T7 promoter, N- or C- terminal His tag and TEV protease site, ligation independent cloning LIC) routinely used for HTP, and PCR was used to amplify genomic DNA. Constructs were transformed into several *E. coli* expression host cells, e.g. BL21Gold/Star, C41 or C43 strains, which were shown successful for the expression of many bacterial membrane proteins. Small-scale cultures (~50 ml) were used to test the expression levels using different growth media and temperature. Solubilisation was also tested in various detergents. Purification followed by affinity chromatography (Ni-NTA and reverse Ni-NTA) by size-exclusion to assess sample purity and homogeneity. The results are summarised in Tables 1-7 of the Appendix. If sufficient purified protein was available, crystallisation screens were performed using nanolitre dispensing robots (Mosquito TTP Labtech) for traditional vapour diffusion and lipidic cubic phase techniques at 4° and 22°C. In parallel, the quality of protein sample was assessed for cryo-EM analysis. For this, detergents were replaced by amphiphols or protein reconstituted in nano-discs to reduce the background noise. Samples were screened by cryo-EM and initial re-constructions derived from class averages.

4.3 Summary of results

Of the 97 targets selected from different mycobacteria strains, 54 genes were cloned, 28 expressed, 8 proteins purified, and 6 proteins solubilised in 3 detergents. Of the purified proteins, the structure of five proteins have been solved by cryo-EM (EmbB from *M. vanbaalenii* M and four proteins from *M. abscessus*), one of these proteins was analysed by single particle cryo-EM⁷ (AftD from *M. abscessus*). One protein has been crystallised.

Examples of results generated at each stage of the protocol are shown in the following figures.

⁶J. Love et al., The New York Consortium on Membrane Protein Structure (NYCOMPS): a high-throughput platform for structural genomics of integral membrane proteins. *J Struct Funct Genomics* 11, 191-199 (2010).

⁷Tan et al. Cryo-EM Structures and Regulation of Arabinofuranosyltransferase AftD from Mycobacteria <https://doi.org/10.1101/2019.12.22.885152> (2020) BioRxiv.

Figure 11. SDS-PAGE of small-scale expression screen from 15 ml cell culture. The red arrows indicate the bands corresponding to the expected molecular weight of each target. Expressing targets: A5, A9 (faint band), A10, A11, A12 and B1. Negative targets: A3, A8, B3. See tables in Appendix for the identification of targets.

Figure 12. SDS-PAGE of Ni-NTA purification steps for H9 – EmbB from *Mycobacterium vanbaalenii* PYR-1 from 2 - 4 L cell culture MW – Ladder; FT – Flow-through; W – Wash; 1st Ni – Elution from 1st Ni-NTA; 2nd Ni – Flow through of 2nd Ni-NTA after His-tag removal by TEV protease.

Figure 13. Detergent Screens for IMP solubilisation: Detergent screens of A12 EmbB (left) and B1 EmbC (right) by SEC. DDM: n-Dodecyl- β -D-Maltopyranoside, DM: n-Decyl- β -D-Maltopyranoside, NM n-Nonyl- β -D-Maltopyranoside, OG: n-Octyl- β -D-Glucopyranoside, LDAO: Lauryldimethylamine-N-Oxide, CYMAL5: 5-Cyclohexyl-1-Pentyl- β -D- Maltosides seem to be the best detergents to solubilise both EmbB and EmbC.

H9 - EmbB

Figure 14. Detergent screen of H9 EmbB. DDM: n-Dodecyl- β -D-Maltopyranoside, DM: n-Decyl- β -D-Maltopyranoside, NM: n-Nonyl- β -D-Maltopyranoside, OM: n-Octyl- β -D-Maltopyranoside, NG: n-Nonyl- β -D-Glucopyranoside, OG: n-Octyl- β -D-Glucopyranoside, OTG: n-Octyl β -D-thioglucoopyranoside, LDAO: Lauryldimethylamine-N-Oxide, CYMAL5: 5-Cyclohexyl-1-Pentyl- β -D-Maltoside, CYMAL4: 4-Cyclohexyl-1-Butyl- β -D-Maltoside, DMNG: Decyl Maltose Neopentyl Glycol, OGNG: Octyl Glucose Neopentyl Glycol. Maltosides are suitable detergents to solubilise EmbB.

Figure 15. Purification of EmbB and AftD. **(A)** Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) elution profile of EmbB reconstituted in 1E3D1 nanodiscs. **(B)** SDS-PAGE of the EmbB fractions collected during SEC. **(C)** Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) elution profile of AftD reconstituted in 1E3D1 nanodiscs. **(D)** SDS-PAGE of the AftD fractions collected during SEC.

Figure 16. Preliminary EM analysis of EmbB: Representative 2D class averages of vitrified EmbB dimer presenting opposite polarity **(A)**, same polarity **(B)**. **(C)** 2D classes of full data set (22,000 particles). Particles were picked ab initio using DoG picker, contrast transfer function (CTF) was estimated using CTFFind3 and 2D classification was performed using Xmipp CL2D, all within the Appion pipeline.

Figure 17. Preliminary structure of EmbB, with 7.8 Å of resolution. **Right panel:** bottom and side view of EmbB dimer. **Left panel:** several structural features of EmbB in nanodisc - Top: Cytosolic domains (bottom view), transmembrane domains (sliced); Bottom: Side view of transmembrane domains and monomer representation overlaid with dimer.

Figure 18. Summary of the workflow for the production and structural analysis of bacterial membrane proteins expressed in *E. coli*.

5. Summary and conclusions

Work package 7 is focused on sample preparation for structural biology applications, with the aim of streamlining and integrating methods. In D7.1 we report our work on optimising the production of integral membrane proteins (IMPs) in different expression systems, to provide standardised workflows incorporating key stop/go decision points. We have approached our task in two different ways. At ITQB (P14) the production of all members of two families of mycobacterial enzymes in *E. coli* has been addressed and a large set of homologues has been triaged through expression and detergent solubilisation screening. This demonstrated the importance of parallel processing and led to the identification of a number of proteins suitable for structural analysis by single particle cryo-EM. In a different approach, UOXF (P2) and HZI (3rd party P1) have collaborated to compare the expression of a small set of mammalian IMPs in two different eukaryotic cell systems derived from humans and insects respectively. The test set was chosen to include proteins known to be expressible in these cells in order to benchmark the optimised protocols. With the aim of rapidly and cost-effectively generating data, proteins were expressed transiently at small scale. By optimising these steps, useful results were obtained that would inform decisions on whether to proceed with further work. Although transient transfection of the human kidney derived cell line (HEK and its derivatives) is well established, significant protocol improvements have been made. Transient transfection of insect cells is a new technology and as far as we know not previously used for the expression of IMPs. Preliminary data presented in this report indicate that it is a viable alternative to HEK transients but further comparative work will be required to compare the products of these two expression systems.

Access to all the optimised workflows reported here is available through collaboration directly with the partners involved and the ULTRA grant will support a user project at HZI as a pilot for this collaborative approach. The methods developed by UOXF will be incorporated into the protocols used by the Membrane Protein Laboratory, one of the facilities of Instruct-UK on the Harwell Campus. Results of the work supported by ULTRA in WP7 will be disseminated through scientific publications for which manuscripts are in preparation.

Appendix: Summary of the results for MtB targets expressed in *E. coli*

1. Arabinofuranosyltransferases (AftABCD)

Table 1. AftA targets. ENA ID: European Nucleotide Archive identification nr (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena>). DDM: n-Dodecyl- β -D-Maltopyranoside, DM: n-Decyl- β -D-Maltopyranoside, NM: n-Nonyl- β -D-Maltopyranoside. Output: 13 select, 8 cloned, 4 expressed, 2 purified, 2 tested detergents.

ID	ENA ID	Organism/Protein	Identity to <i>M.tuberculosis</i> (%)	MW (kDa)	Predicted TM domains	Cloning	Expression screen	Scale-up (500 mL)	Detergent screen	Purification yield (mg/0.5 L)
A1	ENA CDO45093 CDO45093.1	<i>Mycobacteriumbovis</i> AF2122/97	99	70	13	√	-			
A8	ENA EUA63955 EUA63955.1	<i>Mycobacteriumabscessus</i> 1948	66	68	13	√	+	-		
B12	ENA AFM19668 AFM19668.1	<i>Mycobacteriumchubuense</i> NBB4	65	71	10	-				
C1	ENA ACC43758 ACC43758.1	<i>Mycobacteriummarinum</i> M	79	70	13	-				
C2	ENA ABP43658 ABP43658.1	<i>Mycobacteriumgilvum</i> PYR-GCK	67	67	13	√	-			
C6	ENA AIU11367 AIU11367.1	<i>Mycobacterium smegmatis</i> str. MC2 155	69	67	12	-				
C9	ENA AFC41461 AFC41461.1	<i>Mycobacteriumintracellulare</i> ATCC 13950	76	68	13	√	-			
F1	ENA ABM16394 ABM16394.1	<i>Mycobacteriumvanbaalenii</i> PYR-1	67	68	13	√	+	+	DDM, DM, NM	1.23
F3	ENA AGP61782 AGP61782.1	<i>Mycobacteriumyongonense</i> 05-1390	77	68	13	√	+	-		
F4	ENA EHB54850 EHB54850.1	<i>Mycobacteriumrhodesiae</i> JS60	70	66	13	-				
F5	ENA AGZ51273 AGZ51273.1	<i>Mycobacteriumkansasi</i> ATCC 12478	81	70	13	-				
F7	ENA CDQ43571 CDQ43571.1	<i>Mycobacteriumneoaurum</i>	67	67	11	√	+	+	DDM, DM, NM	ND
F8	ENA AAS02550 AAS02550.1	<i>Mycobacteriumavium</i> subsp. <i>paratuberculosis</i> K-10	77	75	11	√	-			

Table 2. AftB targets. Output: 14 selected, 8 cloned, 4 expressed.

ID	ENA ID	Organism/Protein	Identity to tuberculosis(%)	MW (kDa)	Predicted TM domains	Cloning	Expression screen	Scale-up (500 mL)	Detergent screen	Purification yield (mg/0.5L)
A2	ENA CDO45107 CDO45107.1	<i>Mycobacteriumbovis AF2122/97</i>	99	69	9	√	-			
A9	ENA EUA63936 EUA63936.1	<i>Mycobacteriumabscessus 1948</i>	65	71	10	√	+	-		
C7	ENA CCP46634 CCP46634.3	<i>Mycobacteriumtuberculosis H37Rv</i>	100	69	9	√	+	-		
C8	ENA AAS02532 AAS02532.1	<i>Mycobacteriumaviumsubsp. paratuberculosis K-10</i>	82	70	9	-				
D8	ENA ABP43645 ABP43645.1	<i>Mycobacterium gilvum PYR-GCK</i>	71	70	9	-				
D9	ENA AGP61763 AGP61763.1	<i>Mycobacteriumyongonense 05-1390</i>	82	72	10	√	+	-		
D10	ENA AFC41442 AFC41442.1	<i>Mycobacteriumintracellulare ATCC 13950</i>	82	72	10	√	+	-		
D11	ENA ABM16411 ABM16411.1	<i>Mycobacteriumvanbaalenii PYR-1</i>	70	72	9	√	-			
D12	ENA EHB54870 EHB54870.1	<i>Mycobacteriumrhodesiae JS60</i>	68	73	10	-				
E1	ENA CDM79377 CDM79377.1	<i>Mycobacteriummarinum E11</i>	85	73	10	-				
E2	ENA AIR19061 AIR19061.1	<i>Mycobacteriumkansasii 662</i>	86	73	10	√	-			
E3	ENA ABK75671 ABK75671.1	<i>Mycobacterium smegmatis str. MC2 155</i>	72	70	9	-				
E4	ENA AFM19681 AFM19681.1	<i>Mycobacteriumchubuense NBB4</i>	69	72	11	-				
E5	ENA CDQ43590 CDQ43590.1	<i>Mycobacteriumneoaurum</i>	68	69	11	√	-			

Table 3. AftC targets. Output: 13 select, 11 cloned, 6 expressed.

ID	ENA ID	Organism/Protein	Identity to <i>M tuberculosis</i> (%)	MW (kDa)	Predicted TM domains	Cloning	Expression screen	Scale-up (500 mL)	Detergent screen	Purification yield (mg/0.5L)
A3	ENA CDO43956 CDO43956.1	<i>Mycobacterium bovis</i> AF2122/97	99	49	8	√	+	-		
A10	ENA EUA61591 EUA61591.1	<i>Mycobacterium abscessus</i> 1948	64	47	7	√	+	-		
C10	ENA ABK72123 ABK72123.1	<i>Mycobacterium smegmatis</i> str. MC2 155	70	49	6	-				
C11	ENA AFC44620 AFC44620.1	<i>Mycobacterium intracellulare</i> ATCC 13950	84	50	8	√	-			
C12	ENA AGZ53302 AGZ53302.1	<i>Mycobacterium kansasii</i> ATCC 12478	90	49	8	√	-			
D1	ENA ABP46386 ABP46386.1	<i>Mycobacterium gilvum</i> PYR-GCK	71	48	9	√	+	-		
D2	ENA CDQ43952 CDQ43952.1	<i>Mycobacterium neoaurum</i>	72	48	8	√	+	-		
E6	ENA EHB50241 EHB50241.1	<i>Mycobacterium rhodesiae</i> JS60	84	49	7	√	-			
E7	ENA AFM16967 AFM16967.1	<i>Mycobacterium chubuense</i> NBB4	88	49	9	√	-			
E8	ENA AAS05110 AAS05110.1	<i>Mycobacterium avium</i> subsp. <i>paratuberculosis</i> K-10	72	49	8	√	+	-		
E9	ENA AGP64972 AGP64972.1	<i>Mycobacterium yongonense</i> 05-1390	72	50	8	√	+	-		
E10	ENA ACC40492 ACC40492.1	<i>Mycobacterium marinum</i>	83	50	8	-				
F9	ENA ABM13300 ABM13300.1	<i>Mycobacterium vanbaalenii</i> PYR-1	70	48	9	√	-			

Table 4. AftD targets. Output: 14 select, 3 cloned, 1 expressed, 1 purified, 1 tested in detergents, 1x 3D structure by EM underway.

ID	ENA ID	Organism/Protein	Identity to <i>Myc. tuberculosis</i> (%)	MW (kDa)	Predicted TM domains	Cloning	Expression screen	Scale-up (500 mL)	Detergent screen	Purification yield (mg/0.5L)
A4	ENA CDO41480 CDO41480.1	<i>Mycobacterium bovis</i> AF2122/97	99	146	9	√	-			
B5	ENA CCP42964 CCP42964.3	<i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> H37Rv	100	146	9	-				
D3	ENA ABK71542 ABK71542.1	<i>Mycobacterium smegmatis</i> str. MC2 155	71	148	12	-				
D4	ENA AGZ51741 AGZ51741.1	<i>Mycobacterium kansasii</i> ATCC 12478	82	148	13	√	-			
D5	ENA ACC38960 ACC38960.1	<i>Mycobacterium marinum</i>	80	146	7	-				
D6	ENA AFM15049 AFM15049.1	<i>Mycobacterium chubuense</i> NBB4	70	145	12	-				
D7	ENA ADT97050 ADT97050.1	<i>Mycobacterium gilvum</i> Spyr1	69	148	13	-				
E11	ENA AAS06236 AAS06236.1	<i>Mycobacterium avium</i> subsp. <i>paratuberculosis</i> K-10	78	145	9	-				
E12	ENA EHB55421 EHB55421.1	<i>Mycobacterium rhodesiae</i> JS60	72	149	13	-				
F2	ENA CDQ42439 CDQ42439.1	<i>Mycobacterium neoaurum</i> F5/8	67	148	13	-				
F6	ENA AGP66385 AGP66385.1	<i>Mycobacterium yongonense</i> 05-1390	79	146	13	-				
F10	ENA ABM11102 ABM11102.1	<i>Mycobacterium vanbaalenii</i> PYR-1	67	147	10	-				
H11	ENA EUA63217 EUA63217.1	<i>Mycobacterium abscessus</i> 1948 F5/8	62	149	12	√	+	+	DDM	0.49
H12	ENA AFC46048 AFC46048.1	<i>Mycobacterium intracellulare</i> ATCC 13950	79	146	13	-				

2. Arabinosyltransferases (EmbABC)

Table 5. EmbA targets. Output-14 select, 8 cloned, 3 expressed.

ID	ENA ID	Organism/Protein	Identity to <i>Myc. tuberculosis</i> (%)	MW (kDa)	Predicted TM domains	Cloning	Expression screen	Scale-up (500 mL)	Detergent screen	Purification yield (mg/0.5L)
A5	ENA CDO45095 CDO45095.1	<i>Mycobacteriumbovis</i> AF2122/97 EmbA	99	116	13	√	+	-		
A11	ENA EUA63951 EUA63951.1	<i>Mycobacteriumabscessus</i> 1948 EmbA	65	114	12	√	+	-		
B4	ENA AAC45280 AAC45280.1	<i>Mycobacteriumtuberculosis</i> H37Rv EmbA	99	116	13	√	-			
B8	ENA ACC43760 ACC43760.1	<i>Mycobacteriummarinum</i> M EmbA	86	118	13	-				
B11	ENA AFM19670 AFM19670.1	<i>Mycobacteriumchubuense</i> NBB4 EmbA	69	115	13	-				
C5	ENA ABP43656 ABP43656.1	<i>Mycobacteriumgilvum</i> PYR-GCK EmbA	67	114	12	√	-			
F11	ENA AFP42646 AFP42646.1	<i>Mycobacterium smegmatis</i> str. MC2 155 EmbA	68	117	13	-				
G2	ENA AFC41456 AFC41456.1	<i>Mycobacteriumintracellulare</i> ATCC 13950 embA	82	115	14	-				
G5	ENA AAS02546 AAS02546.1	<i>Mycobacteriumavium</i> subsp. <i>paratuberculosis</i> K-10 EmbA	82	117	14	√	-			
G8	ENA AGP61777 AGP61777.1	<i>Mycobacteriumyongonense</i> 05-1390 embA	82	116	14	-				
G11	ENA CDQ43576 CDQ43576.1	<i>Mycobacteriumneoaurum</i> EmbA	68	116	13	√				
G12	ENA EHB54852 EHB54852.1	<i>Mycobacteriumrhodesiae</i> JS60 EmbA	71	116	12	-				
H1	ENA ABM16396 ABM16396.1	<i>Mycobacteriumvanbaalenii</i> PYR-1 EmbA	69	116	13	√	-			
H2	ENA AGZ51276 AGZ51276.1	<i>Mycobacteriumkansaii</i> ATCC 12478 EmbA	87	115	13	√	+	-		

Table 6. EmbB targets. Output-15 select, 9 cloned, 5 expressed, 3 purified, 2 tested in detergents, 1 crystallised, 1x 3D structure by EM underway.

ID	ENA ID	Organism/Protein	Identity to <i>Myc. tuberculosis</i> (%)	MW (kDa)	Predicted TM domains	Cloning	Expression screen	Scale-up (500 mL)	Detergent screen	Purification yield (mg/0.5L)
A6	ENA CDO45096 CDO45096.1	<i>Mycobacteriumbovis AF2122/97</i>	99	118	13	√	-			
A12	ENA EUA63949 EUA63949.1	<i>Mycobacteriumabscessus 1948</i>	68	73	8	√	+	+	DDM, DM, NM	0.63
B3	ENA AAC45281 AAC45281.1	<i>Mycobacteriumtuberculosis H37Rv</i>	99	118	12	√	-			
B7	ENA ACC43761 ACC43761.1	<i>Mycobacteriummarinum M</i>	88	116	12	-				
B9	ENA AFM19671 AFM19671.1	<i>Mycobacteriumchubuense NBB4</i>	71	115	13	-				
B10	ENA AFM19669 AFM19669.1	<i>Mycobacteriumchubuense NBB4</i>	69	116	12	-				
C4	ENA ABP43655 ABP43655.1	<i>Mycobacteriumgilvum PYR-GCK</i>	68	115	13	√	+	-		
F12	ENA ABK72840 ABK72840.1	<i>Mycobacterium smegmatis str. MC2 155</i>	68	117	13	-				
G3	ENA AFC41455 AFC41455.1	<i>Mycobacteriumintracellulare ATCC 13950</i>	83	115	12	√	+			
G6	ENA AAS02545 AAS02545.1	<i>Mycobacteriumaviumsubsp. paratuberculosis K-10</i>	83	115	12	√	+	+	DDM	0.23
G9	ENA AGP61776 AGP61776.1	<i>Mycobacteriumyongonense 05-1390</i>	83	115	12	√	+	-		
H7	ENA KEP38884 KEP38884.1	<i>Mycobacteriumkansasii</i>	89	117	11	√	-			
H8	ENA AEV72557 AEV72557.1	<i>Mycobacteriumrhodesiae NBB3</i>	75	114	13	-				
H9	ENA ABM16397 ABM16397.1	<i>Mycobacteriumvanbaalenii PYR-1</i>	70	115	13	√	++	++	DDM, DM, NM	0.896
H10	ENA AHC23140 AHC23140.1	<i>Mycobacteriumneoaurum VKM Ac-1815D</i>	68	115	13	-				

Table 7. EmbC targets. Output-14 select, 7 cloned, 5 expressed, 2 purified, 2 tested in detergents

ID	ENA ID	Organism/Protein	Identity to <i>Myc. tuberculosis</i> (%)	MW (kDa)	Predicted TM domains	Cloning	Expression screen	Scale-up (500 mL)	Detergent screen	Purification yield (mg/0.5L)
A7	ENA CDO45094 CDO45094.1	<i>Mycobacterium bovis</i> AF2122/97	99	118	13	-				
B1	ENA EUA63954 EUA63954.1	<i>Mycobacterium abscessus</i> 1948	68	117	11	√	+	+	DDM, NM, DM	0.49
B2	ENA AAC45279 AAC45279.1	<i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i> H37Rv	99	117	13	-				
B6	ENA ACC43759 ACC43759.1	<i>Mycobacterium marinum</i> M	86	117	14	-				
B10	ENA AFM19669 AFM19669.1	<i>Mycobacterium chubuense</i> NBB4	74	116	12	-				
C3	ENA ABP43657 ABP43657.1	<i>Mycobacterium gilvum</i> PYR-GCK	73	115	14	√	-			
G1	ENA ABK72375 ABK72375.1	<i>Mycobacterium smegmatis</i> str. MC2 155	75	115	10	-				
G4	ENA AFC41460 AFC41460.1	<i>Mycobacterium intracellulare</i> ATCC 13950	85	114	13	√	+	+	DDM	0.4
G7	ENA AAS02549 AAS02549.1	<i>Mycobacterium avium</i> subsp. <i>paratuberculosis</i> K-10	85	117	13	√	+	-		
G10	ENA AGP61781 AGP61781.1	<i>Mycobacterium yongonense</i> 05-1390	85	114	13	√	+	-		
H3	ENA AEV72559 AEV72559.1	<i>Mycobacterium rhodesiae</i> NBB3	76	114	14	-				
H4	ENA CDQ43572 CDQ43572.1	<i>Mycobacterium neoaurum</i>	71	115	13	√	+	-		
H5	ENA AGZ51274 AGZ51274.1	<i>Mycobacterium kansasii</i> ATCC 12478	87	117	14	√	-			
H6	ENA ABM16395 ABM16395.1	<i>Mycobacterium vanbaalenii</i> PYR-1	73	116	10	-				

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